

ROLE OF HERBO-MINERAL MEDICINES IN AYURVEDIC GYNECOLOGY AND OBSTETRICS: A REVIEW STUDY**Dr. Bhavin Chavda^{1*}, Dr. Kunal Gurav²**

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ABSTRACT

Herbo-mineral preparations play a major role in curing diseases in human beings. These preparations are appreciated for their quick effectiveness, smaller dosages, longer shelf life etc. In various ayurvedic literatures, therapeutic efficacy of herbo-mineral formulations for obstetrics and gynecology is significantly highlighted. These formulations helps in addressing various conditions such as menstrual irregularities, reproductive challenges, menopausal symptoms, age-related degenerative disorders, infertility, antenatal care and post natal care. This research focuses on such herbo-mineral formulations and their impact on obstetrics and gynecological conditions. As knowledge of these formulations is vital for successful practice. These medicine forms represent an important limb of treatment for female health.

KEYWORDS: Herbo-Mineral Medicines, Prasuti Tantra, Stree-Roga.

INTRUDUCTION

Obstetrics and Gynecology (OB-GYN) is a combined medical branch focused on women's reproductive health; it is also known as Stree Roga Evam Prasuti Tantra in the Ayurveda system of medicine. Prasuti Tantra.^[1] mainly focuses on pregnancy, prenatal care, labor and delivery, and postpartum care, including the management of high-risk pregnancies. Stree Roga.^[2] Primarily addresses non-pregnant care, including annual examinations, various

menstruation related problems, Sexually Transmitted Diseases, pelvic pain, and cancer screenings. These have been a leading cause of complications during pregnancy, childbirth, and postnatal period at a global level, as well as leading cause of death and disability among reproductive- aged women. Disorder related to pregnancy and parturition requires utmost care due to significant biological, physical, social, and emotional changes.^[3]

The importance of the subject Rasashastra is mentioned in terms of its therapeutic benefits, not just for pharmaceutical utilities. These include *alpa matra* (effectiveness in very small doses), *aruchi* (does not cause anorexia), and *kshipra arogyadayi* (quick in action in providing health benefits).^[4]

Herbo-mineral Preparations possess *deepana* (metabolic-enhancing) and *pachana* (digestive) properties. To indicate the importance of *Rasachikitsa*, it is mentioned in the texts of Rasashastra that for the treatment of curable diseases, *Bheshaja chikitsa* (treatment by plant drugs) is considered best, whereas for the treatment of incurable diseases, *Rasa chikitsa* is considered a superior therapeutic options. These herbo-mineral combinations are utilized in the treatment of gynecological and obstetric disorders. Thus, this review article attempt to compile the information on regarding the therapeutic application of *rasaushadhi* mentioned in various classical texts of Rasashastra for different obstetric and gynecological conditions.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

The aim of this literary research is to conduct a detailed study and review of herbo-mineral formulations used in obstetric and gynecological conditions.

MATEREALS AND METHODS

The literary sources for data collection include are various classical Rasashastra text books, *Samhitas*, and research Papers that provide detail explanations of herbo mineral formulations, including their names, indications, dosages and *anupana*. After the collection of data, the herbo-mineral Preparations were analyzed according to their usefulness and uniqueness.

Table No. 1: Showing herbo-mineral formulation used in gynecological disorder.

Sr.No.	Rasaushadhi	Indication	Dose	Anupana	Reference
1	Pradarantaka Lauha	Shweta Pradara, Rakta Pradara, Nila Pradara, Pitta Pradara, Yonishula	250 mg	Sharkara, Madhu, Ghrita	B.R.66/79-83, RTSSPS Part 2 Stree Roga Chikitsa 16
2	Pradarari Lauha	Shweta Pradara, Rakta Pradara, Nila Pradara, Pitta Pradara,	5 gm	Kusuma mula Kwatha	B.R.66/74-78
3	Pradarantaka Rasa	Asadhya Pradara Neela, Shweta pradara, Raktapradara (RTSSPS)	250 mg	Madhu, Amalaki Swarasa	B.R.66/49-51, RTSSPS Part 1 Stree Roga Chikitsa (138)
4	Sarvangasundra Rasa	All Types of Pradara	250 mg	Madhu	B.R.66/52-56, RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana (151)
5	Pradarari Rasa	Pradara, Basti vedana,	250 mg	Ashokadi Kwatha Tandulodaka, Madhu	B.R.66/57-61
6	Pradararipu Churna	Kashtasadhya Pradara	375 mg	Madhu	B.R.66/62
7	Madhukadya Avleha	Pradara, Yonishula ,Mutraroga	10- 20 gm	Godugdha	B.R.66/35-41
8	Ratnaprabha Vati	All Types of Stree Roga	125 mg	Balamula Kwatha, Dugdha, Bhringraja Svarasa	B.R.66/63-67
9	Shilajatu Vatika	Rakta pradara	125 mg	Dadima Swarasa, Dugdha, Mamsarasa, Jala	B.R.66/68-73
10	Lakshmana Lauha	All Stree Roga	500 mg	Madhu, Ghrita	B.R.66/84-86
11	Patrangasava	Shweta Pradara, Rakta Pradara	20-40 ml	Jala	B.R.66/122-126
12	Raja Pravatini Vati	Rajodaha, Kashtapradara,	375 mg	Koshna Jala	B.R.67/58-60
13	Kumarkalpadruma Ghritam	Vandhya, Shandha Yoni, Rajodosha,	10-20 gm	Aja -Dugdha, Go-Dugdha	B.R 67/91-112
14	Garbhachiintamani Rasa	Pradara	250 mg	Dugdha	RTSSPS Part 1 Kharaliya Rasayana (140)
15	Garbhachintamani Rasa 2 nd	Garbhini Roga, Sutika Roga, Pradara	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 68/87-90,
16	Rasashardula Rasa	Sutika Roga, Stree Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 68/77-79
17	Shilajatvadi Churna	Yoni Kandu	1-2 gm	Jala	B.R.104/9-10
18	Chandraprabha Vati	Raktapradara Kastartava, Yoni Roga Anaratava,	12 gm - 375 mg (RTSSPS) 250-500 mg	- Takra, Mastu, Mamsarasa, Aja Dugdha, Shita Jala, Ghrita	Sha.Sam.M.Kha.7/40-49, R.Chi..9/32-38 RTSSPS Part 1, Gutika Prakarana 6
19	Yogaraja Guggulu	Rajodosha,	125-250	-	Sha.Sam.M.Kha.7/56-69,

			mg		
20	Purna Chandra-Rasa	Stree-Roga	500 mg	Shalmali Churna/ Kwatha, Madhu, Ghrita	R.Chi..9/36-38
21	Maha Lakshmi vilasa Rasa	Stree Roga	250 mg	Mamsarasa,Dughda, Dadhi, Manda,Sura ,Sidhu	R.Chi..9/28-40
22	Brihata Shankeshwar Rasa	Somaroga	250 mg	Go Dugdha, Aja Dugdha	R.Chi..9/30-36
23	Gaganadi Lauha	Somaroga	1-2 gm 500 mg	Madhu	R.Chi..9/1-3, B.R. 86/18-20,
24	Tadkeshwara Rasa 1 st	Somaroga	500 mg 125 mg	Madhu	R.Chi..9/4-5 , B.R. 86/23-25
25	Tadkeshwara Rasa 2 nd	Somaroga	375 mg	Madhu	R.Chi..9/6-7
26	Someshwara Rasa	Somaroga	500 mg	Madhu	R.Chi..9/8-13
27	Somnatha Rasa 1 st	Somaroga, Pradar, Yonishoola	375 mg	Jala	R.Chi..9/8-13,
28	Somnatha Rasa	Somaroga, Yonishoola, Pradara	1250 mg	Madhu	B.R. 86/24-27
29	Somnatha Rasa 2 nd	Somaroga	250 mg	Madhu	R.Chi..9/18-23
30	Brihada Somnatha Rasa	Somaroga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R. 86/28-34
31	Bahumutranataka Rasa	Somaroga, Bahumutra	250 mg	Madhu	B.R. 86/35-38
32	Hemanatha Rasa	Somaroga, Bahumutra,	375 mg	As Per Dosha	B.R. 86/43-47
33	Vasantakusumakara Rasa	Somaroga	375 mg	Madhu	B.R. 86/48-53.
34	Sarveshwara Rasa	Raktaja Gulma,	125-250 mg	Madhu	R.Chi..9/89, B.R.32/132-133
35	Gulmashardula Rasa	Raktaja Gulma	375 mg	Ardraka Swarasa, Ushna Jala	R.Chi..9/10-13 B.R.32/106-109
36	Kankayana Gutika	Raktaja Gulma	1 gm	Ushtra Dugdha	R.Chi..9/14-20
37	Panchanana Rasa	Raktaja Gulma	250 mg	Chinchadala Swarasa	B.R,32/127-128
38	Gulmavajrini Vatika	Raktaja Gulma	125 mg	Ushna Jala	B.R,32/129-131
39	Chandrakala Rasa	Raktapradara,	250 mg	Vasa Swarasa	R.R.S.13/7-16 , RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 63
40	Mehari Rasa	Pradara	375 mg	Madhu, Guduchi Satva, Pippali Churna	R.R.S.17/120-123
41	Yogaraja Guggulu Vati 1 st	Yonidosha, Rajodosha, Vatavyadhi	375 mg	Ushna Jala	R.R.S.21/120-129
42	Pushyanuga Churna	Raktapradara, Yonidosha, Rajodosha	3 gm	Madhu	R.R.S. 25/101-105

43	Purnachandrodaya Rasa 2	Pradara, Yonivyapada	1 gm	Shalmali Swarasa	R.R.S. 27/23-25
44	Madanasanjeevana Rasa	Pradara, Vajikarana	750 mg	Madhu , Ghrita, Sharkara , Dugdha	R.R.S. 27/85-92
45	Lakshmi vilasa Rasa (Naradiya)	Makkala Shool, Stree Roga	65.5-125 mg	Madhu, Mamsarasa,	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 25
46	Suvarna Malini vasanta	Pradara	125-250 mg	Pippali Churna, Madhu, Guduchi Satva	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 32
47	Madhumalini vasanta	Shweta pradara	125-250 mg	Sharkara, Ghrita, Dugdha	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 33
48	Laghmalini Vasanta	Pradara	125-250 mg	Madhu, Pippali, Dugdha, Jala	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 34
49	Samshamani Vati	Pradara	500-1000 mg	Dugdha	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 35
50	Bolabaddha Rasa	Rakta pradara	500-1500 mg	Navaneeta, Sharkara, Madhu	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 55
51	Kamdudha Rasa	Pradara	125-375 mg	Jeeraka, Sharkara	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 80
52	Panchanimba Churna	Pradara	3- 6 masha	Khadira Tvak Kwatha	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 130
53	Vatibhakesari Rasa	Rakta pradara	15.625 mg	Madhu, Ghrita	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya Rasayana 163
54	Rajapravartini Vati/Kasisadi Vati	Kashtartva, Anartava, Garbhasaya Shuddhi	500 mg	Madhu, Ghrita	RTSSPS Part 1, Gutika Prakarana 16
55	Pradarantaka Vati	Rakta pradara	250-500 mg	Madhu, Tandulodaka	RTSSPS Part 1, Gutika Prakarana 17
56	Kanyalohadi Vati	Kashtartava , Anartava	500 mg	-	RTSSPS Part 1, Gutika Prakarana 34
57	Pradarantaka Churna	Shwetapradara, Raktapradara	6 gm	Tandulodaka , Sharkara	RTSSPS Part 1, Churna Prakarana 30
58	Kumaryasava	Nashtartava	15-30 ml	Jala	RTSSPS Part 1, Asavadi Prakarana 30
59	Saraswatarishta	Rajonivrutti Janya Vikara	15-30 ml	Jala	RTSSPS Part 1, Asavadi Prakarana 11
60	Vaikratna Vasantakusumakara	Somaroga	125-250 mg	Madhu	RTSSPS Part 2 Bahumutra 3
61	Kasisadi Churna	Yoni Paichilya	-	Madhu	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 1
62	Pushyanuga Churna	Yoni Strava	-	-	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 1
63	Pippalyadi Churna	Yoni Strava	125 mg	Madhu	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 1
64	Tutthadi Lepa	Yoni Arsha	External application	Madhu	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 1
65	Gairikadi Churna	Yoni Kanda	for yoni Dhupana	-	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 1
66	Gokshuradi Guggulu	Pradara	-	-	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 1
67	Krishnamrutikadi Churna	Asrigdara	-	Madhu, Tandulodaka	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 2
68	Khandakadya	Vandhyatva	Vidalapada	Go Dugdha	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 5

	Lauha		matra		
69	Daruharidradi Lepa	Updamsa	Lepa (External application)	-	P.V.T. Part 2 Chapter 6

Table No. 2: Showing herbo-mineral formulation used in obstetrics disorder.

Sr.No.	Rasaushadhi	Indication	Dose	Anupana	Reference
1	Nashtapushpantak Rasa	Vandhyatwa, Yoni Shool, Ritu shool	250 mg	Madhu	B.R.67/51-57
2	Kumarika Rasa	Makkkal shool, Jarayu shool	250 mg	Triphala Kwath	B.R 67/63-64
3	Vijayadi Vati	Jarayu shool, Kshtaartava	250 mg	Koshna Jala	B.R 67/65-67
4	Somaghritha	Gar bhini Paricharya, Punsavana vidhi, Yoni Dushti, Vandhatva,	10 gm	Go Dugdha	B.R 67/85-91
5	Kumarkalpadruma Ghrita	Vandhya, Shandha Yoni, Rajodsha,	10-20 gm	Aja Dugdha, Go Dugdha	B.R 67/91-112
6	Garbhavilasa Rasa	Garbhini Roga, Ajirna	500 mg	Madhu, Ushna Dugdha	B.R 68/80-81
7	Garbhavinoda Rasa	Garbhini Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 68/82-83
8	Garbhachintamani Rasa 1 st	Garbhini Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 68/84-86
9	Garbhachintamani Rasa 2 nd	Garbhini Roga, Sutika Roga, Pradara	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 68/87-90
10	Garbhachintmani Rasa (Brihat)	Garbhini Daha, Pradara, Sutika Roga	125 mg	Madhu	B.R 68/91-93
11	Indushekhara Rasa	Garbhini Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 68/94-98
12	Saubhagyashunthi Paka 1 st	Sutika Roga	5-10 gm	Dugdha	B.R 69/25-28
13	Sutikavinoda Rasa	Sutika Roga, Garbhini Roga	500 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/63-64
14	Sutikavinoda Rasa (Brihata)	Sutika Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/65-66
15	Sutikari Rasa	Sutika Roga	250 mg 125 mg	Ardraka Swarasa	B.R 69/67-69 RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana 143
16	Sutikaghna Rasa	Sutika Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/70-71
17	Sutikahara Rasa	Sutika Roga	500 mg	Eranda patra Swarasa	B.R 69/72-76
18	Rasashardula Rasa	Sutika Roga, Stree Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/77-79
19	Maha Rasashadrula	Garbhini Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/80-85
20	Mahabhra Vati (1 st)	Sutika Roga	250 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/86-90
21	Mahabhra Vati (2 nd)	Sutika Roga	125 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/91-93
22	Sutikari Rasa	Sutika Roga	500 mg	Prasarini	B.R 69/94-96

				Kwatha	
23	Sutikanto Rasa	Garbhini Roga, Sutika Roga	500 mg	Madhu	B.R 69/97-98
24	Sutikanto Rasa 2 nd	Sutika Roga	250 mg	As Per Dosha	B.R 69/99-101
25	Maha Sutikavallabha Rasa	Sutika Roga, Garbhini Roga	250 mg	Madhu,	B.R 69/102-105
26	Lakshminarayana Rasa	Sutika Roga	750 mg	Ardraka Swarasa	B.R 69/106-111, RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana 21
27	Sutikabharana Rasa	Sutika Roga	62.5 mg	As Per Dosha	B.R 69/112-116, RTSSPS part 1 Kharaliya rasyana 171
28	Vadvamukha Rasa	Prasutivata Hara	-	-	R.M.3/11-13
29	Stree-dravana Lepa	Streebhaga Drava	Lepa	-	R.M.3/11-1
30	Rasachudamani Rasa	Prasuti Vata	-	-	R.Chi.. 9/112-120
31	Brihata Nayika Churna	Sutika Roga	3-6 Gm	Kanji, Dadhi,	R.Chi.. 9/6-13
32	Vijaybhairava Rasa	Sutika Roga	500 Mg	Guda	R.Chi.. 9/44-46
33	Trailokya Tilaka Rasa	Sutika Roga	125 mg	as per dosha	R.R.S.15/66-80
34	Vahnijwala Rasa	Sutika Roga	500 mg	Trikatu Churna	R.R.S.15/889-93
35	Martandishvara Rasa	Vandhatva, Vatavyadhi	250 mg	Go Ghrita, Trikatu , Ardraka Swarasa, Madhu, Maricha	R.R.S.21/62-68
36	Jaya-sundara Rasa	Vandhyatva	125 mg	Ashvaganda, Go Dugdha	R.R.S.22/5-14
37	Ratnabhagottara Rasa	Vandhyatva , Garbhini Roga	125 mg	Madhu, Ashwagandha churna, Go-dugdha	R.R.S. 22/15-20
38	Chakrika bandha Rasa	Vandhyatva	65-125 mg	Madhu	R.R.S. 22/ 23-29
39	Vardhamana Rasa	Vandhyatva, Yoni Vyapada, Sutika Roga	125 mg	Madhu	R.R.S. 22/30-40
40	Drutisara Rasa	Janma Vandhya, Kaka Vandhya , Sutika Roga	125 mg	Madhu	R.R.S. 22/41-46
41	Parpati Rasa	Sutika Roga	125-375 mg	Ghrita, Pippali Churna	R.R.S. 22/113
42	Sutikaroganashana Rasa	Sutika Roga	125 mg	Madhu, Go Dugdha	R.R.S. 22/114
43	Purnachandrodaya Rasa (2 nd)	Pradara, Yonivyapada	1 gm	Shalmali Swarasa	R.R.S. 27/23-25
44	Lakshmi vilasa rasa	Makkala Shula	125-250	Dugdha,	RTSSPS Part 1,

			mg	Madhu, Dadhi	Kharaliya rasayana (24)
45	Lakshmi vilasa rasa (Naradiya)	Makkala Shula, Stree Roga	65.5-125 mg	Madhu, Mamsarasa,	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (25)
46	Brihata Yogaraja Guggulu	Vandhyatva	250 mg	Rasnadi kwatha, Kakolyadi kwatha,	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (90)
47	Sutashekhara Rasa	Sutika Roga	125 mg	Dugdha, Sharkara, Ghrita	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (133)
48	Pratapa lankeshwara Rasa	Sutika Jwara	375-750 mg	Ardraka Swarasa	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (142)
49	Sarvangasundra Rasa	Sutika Roga	62.5-125 mg	Madhu	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (151)
50	Pushpadhanva Rasa	Vandhyatva	125-250 mg	Dugdha, Sharkara,	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (157)
51	Viryashodhana Vati	Garbhini Masanumasika Paricharya	125-250 mg	Madhu	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (158)
52	Brihada Vatachintamani Rasa	Sutika Roga	125-250	Nagavalli Swarasa	RTSSPS Part 2, vatavyadhi, (3)
53	Maha Vataraja Rasa	Sutika Jwara	125-250 mg	Sharkara	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (162)
54	Smrutisagara Rasa	Garbha Vata, Rajonivrutti	62.5-125 mg	Brahmi Swarasa Saraswataristha	RTSSPS Part 1, Kharaliya rasayana (172)
55	Pramehakunjara Kesari	Garbhini Shula	250-500 mg	Madhu	RTSSPS Part 2,prameha (5)

Abbreviation

B.R.^[5,6] – Bhaishajya Ratnavali **R.R.S.**^[7]- Rasaratna Samuccaya **R.Chi.**^[8] – Rasendra Chintamani **R.M.**^[9]- Rasendra Mangala **Sha. Sam.**^[10]- Sharangdhara Samhita **RTSSPS**^[11,12] - Rasatantra saar & Siddhaprayog Sangraha **P.V.T.**^[13,14] - ayurvediya prasutitantra evam Striroga by Prof.Premvati Tewari.

Table No. 3: Showing Research updates of Herbo-mineral formulation used in Obstetrics and Gynecological disorder.

Sr. No	Name of Rasaushadhi	Indication
1	Pushyanuga Churna ^[15]	Shweta Pradara
2	Puhsyangua Churna	Shweta Pradara ^[16]
3	Pradararipu Rasa ^[17]	Asrigdara
4	Bola Parpati ^[18]	Rakta Pradara
5	Pradarantaka Rasa, Pradararipu Rasa, Bola Parpati, Sutashekhara Rasa, Kamdudha Rasa.	Shweta Pradara ^[19]
6	Kasisadi Vaginal Pessary	Shweta Pradara ^[20]
7	Garbhapala Rasa	Pregnancy induced Nausea and Vomiting ^[21]
8	Bolabaddha Rasa, Pushyanuga Churna	Rakta Pradara ^[22]
9	Kumaryassava	Garbhashaya Granthi ^[23]
10	Pushyanuga Churna	Paripluta Yonivyapada ^[24]
11	Chandraprabha Vati, Pushyanuga Churna	Vandhyatva ^[25]
12	Abhra Lauha	Vataja Yonivyapada ^[26]
13	Pushyanuga Churna	Asrigdara ^[27]
14	Punarnava Mandura, Chandraprabha Vati	Uterine Fibroid ^[28]
15	Dhatri Lauha	Vataja Yonivyapada ^[29]
16	Chandraprabha Vati	Asrigdara ^[30]
17	Navayasa Churna	PCOD ^[31]
18	Chandraprabha Vati	Maha Yoni (Uterine Prolapse) ^[32]
19	Agnitundi Vati	PCOD and Infertility ^[33]
20	Pushpadhanva Rasa	Anovulatory factor of Infertility, ^[34]

DISCUSSION

Stree roga and Prasuti Tantra is the Specialized branch of Ayurveda that deals with the health of the women, starting at puberty all up to menopause. It is basically ayurvedic counterpart of Gynecology and Obstetrics.

Stree Roga (Gynecology) This is the medical specialty that focuses on diseases that are unique to the female reproductive system. It includes the Artava Vyapada (Menstrual Disorders) - various menstrual abnormalities (like Raja Kshaya or Asrigadara) based on Dosha imbalances, Yonivyapada (Vaginal/Uterine Disorders) covering infections, anatomical issues, and hormonal imbalances, Vandhyatva (Infertility) treatment and investigation of it into the four essential factors responsible for conception i.e. Ritu (The right timing/ovulation), Kshetra (The healthy field/uterus), Ambu (Proper nourishment/hormones) and Beeja (Healthy ovum/sperm).

Prasuti Tantra deals with the health of the mother from conception through the postnatal period. It includes Garbhadhana (Conception) i.e. focuses on the preparation of the couple (Purvakarma) to ensure a healthy progeny, Garbhini Paricharya (Antenatal Care) Masanumashika Paricharya designed to support the developing fetus and the mother's strength, Prasava (Labor and Delivery) management of normal labor and identification of complications (Mudha Garbha or mal presentations), Sutika Paricharya (Postnatal Care) Specialized care for the mother after delivery to restore the Dhatus (tissues) and balance the Vata Dosha.

To enhance health of women and address several gynecological disorders in the Stree roga and Prasuti Tantra, herbo-mineral preparation (Rasaushadhi) is available in Ayurvedic literature. These are low-dose efficacy where therapeutic effects are obtained at milligram-level doses and a quicker action as compared to strictly herbal options. These formulations further have a long shelf life and a special synergy of herbal and mineral ingredients. Although they have these benefits, their use requires that they are strictly followed with traditional procedures, such as proper purification (Shodhana), preparation (Marana) and administration that is under strict supervision to safeguard the lives of patients.

This research paper establishes inclusive criteria to identify and analyze specific herbo-mineral formulation (Rasaushadhi) from different authoritative classical sources, including the Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Rasa-Tantra Sara Evam Siddha Prayoga Sangraha, Rasendra Chintamani, Sharangadhara Samhita, Rasaratna Samuccaya, and Rasendra Mangala. These books are well known in terms of clinical confirmation and usefulness. Moreover, this paper incorporates the existing literature to analyze how these herbo-mineral combinations find their modern use in the realms of Stree Roga (Gynecology) and Prasuti Tantra (Obstetrics).

According to Table No. 01 (Gynecology) shows that a total of 69 formulations were identified for managing gynecological disorders, sourced from Bhaishajya Ratnavali (27), RTSSPS (22), Rasendra Chintamani (13), Textbook of P.V. Tiwari (12), and Sharangdhara Samhita (2). The pharmaceutical distribution includes 34 Kharaliya Rasasyana, 10 Churna, 07 Vati, 06 Sandhana Kalpana, 04 Lauha Kalpana, 02 Guggulu, 01 Sneha Kalpana, and 01 Avaleha alongwith therapeutic dosages ranging from 125 mg to 1 gm. These recipes are mainly aimed to Pradara (abnormal vaginal discharge) and other Stree Roga by treating the vitiation of Kapha, Pitta, and Rakta Dosha in the Artavavaha Srotasa. The clinical review shows the popularity of Lauha preparations (e.g., Pradarantaka Lauha) due to their

Raktaprasadaka and hematinic actions, Rasaushadhis (e.g., Chandrakala Rasa) due to their potent Stambhana and Rasayana actions and Kashayarasa-dominated preparations such as Pushyanuga Churna. Moreover, there are also specialized formulations, like Raja Pravartini Vati or Vasantakusumakara Rasa, which deal with menstrual regulation and metabolic/reproductive overlaps, such as Somaroga, with a multidimensional ayurvedic approach of Dosha pacification, Stambhana action and Srotasa correction using the strategic use of Anupana, like Madhu or Ushnodaka.

According to Table No. 2 (Obstetric), 55 formulations have been found in obstetrical disorders, of which 27 formulations are found in Bhaishajya Ratnavali, 15 in RTSSPS, 11 in Rasaratna Samuccaya and 02 in Rasendra Mangala. The first thing that strikes one about the table is the usage of formulations that are common in Garbhini Roga (antenatal disorders) and Sutika Roga (postnatal disorders). Nashtapushpanta Rasa, Kumarika Rasa and Vijayadi Vati are primarily prescribed in Vandhyatva and Yonivyapada, which indicates that the drugs help to alleviate reproductive health and fix underlying Dosha imbalances, especially Vata and Pitta. Recipes such as Somaghrita and Kumarkalpa Druma Ghrita discuss the use of Ghrita-based preparations during pregnancy since Ghrita has Rasayana, Balya and Medhya properties that allow the fetus to develop efficiently, increase maternal strength and Anupana such as Go-dugdha (cows milk) to enhance nourishment and bioavailability. Herbo-mineral drugs like Garbhavilasa Rasa, Garbhavinoda Rasa and Garbhachintamani Rasa which are indicated in Garbhasthapaka (pregnancy-sustaining) and Agnideepana effects, and the common use of Madhu as Anupana indicates its Yogavahi properties in drug absorption and efficacy. Some of the formulations that are widely applied in the management of Sutika Roga include Sutikavinoda Rasa, Sutikaghna Rasa and Sutikahara Rasa that mainly work to restore Agni (digestive fire), cut down the Vata aggravation after delivery, bring about uterine involution, promote lactation and maternal strength using vehicles as like Ardraka Swarasa, Eranda Patra Swarasa. The other important observation is that Mahabhra Vati, Rasashardula Rasa, and Lakshminarayana Rasa are repeatedly mentioned, which means that they are universal and can be used in the context of strengthening maternal physiology and managing complications, and they may be adaptogenic and rejuvenative. Topical and supportive treatment like Stree-dravana Lepa and formulations that treat Prasuti Vata make it clear that Ayurvedic therapy does not solely focus on internal drugs but also provides external and supportive therapies, which guarantees holistic treatment. Pharmacologically, herbo-mineral formulations are herbal synergy and mineral potency providing faster action through

Sukshma and Vyavayi properties, less dose requirement (usually 125 to 500 mg) and specific therapeutic actions. These formulations is classically explained very well but scientific validation of safety and efficacy is still needed by clinical studies, standardization and toxicity testing are essential especially in sensitive disorders such as pregnancy.\

Table No.1 and Table No. 2 shows that the unique Features of herbo-mineral formulations. Among the various characteristics of herbo-mineral preparations identified in the analysis is the fact that it has a number of distinct features that distinguish it as contrasted with conventional treatment.

Table No. 3 shows that a few of the classical formulations are being validated by modern day research. Significant ones are Pushyanuga Churna to treat Shweta Pradara, Navayasa Churna and Agnitundi Vati to treat PCOD, Punarnava Mandura and Chandraprabha Vati to treat Uterine Fibroids and Pushpadhanva Rasa to treat infertility.. These advances mark the beginning of a scientifically growing interest in ayurvedic preparations and point to their enormous possibilities of being incorporated into the contemporary gynecological practice. More so, the trend highlights the growing provision of rigorous, evidence-based validation in the clinical field.

CONCLUSION

The summarized information points to the fact that Rasashastra provides a holistic and methodological approach to the treatment of gynecological and obstetrical conditions. They are disease-specific formulations, which are directed towards specific Doshas and which have the proper anupana to back them up. Besides, the association with the contemporary studies concentrates on clinical significance and future prospects of these herbo-mineral preparations. Further clinical trials and pharmacological research is necessary in order to prove their safety and efficacy in a more general practice in the gynecology and obstetrics branch.

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